

MONITORING APPROACH FOR FATIGUE DAMAGE THRESHOLD DETERMINATION IN COMPOSITES CONTAINING FLAWS

C. Batigne, N. Bouslama, J. Wu and A. Maslouhi*

Mechanical Engineering Department, Université de Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author (Ahmed.Maslouhi@usherbrooke.ca)

<https://www.usherbrooke.ca/gmecanique/>

Keywords: Composites, Delamination, Fatigue life, Acoustic emission

1 INTRODUCTION

The presence of manufacturing flaws in composite structures represents a significant limitation for the application of composite materials in primary aeronautical structures. In general, the fabrication of composite structures generates defects that can induce alteration of the mechanical properties and create early failures under dynamic loading. Delamination can be often caused by pre-existing manufacturing defects and also originated from several sources such as residual stresses from curing, geometric discontinuities, edges, impact damage [1]. After the initiation, it followed a redistribution of the stresses in mode I, mode II and mixed around the defect and in the plies, which strongly favors the propagation of the delamination in the laminate, that may reduce the strength and fatigue life of the structure.

Therefore, for a safe design of composite structures, it is essential to evaluate the effect of flaws on damage propagation and the endurance limit of the materials. The long-term objective of our research program is to develop predictive modeling methodologies based on experimental fatigue data, which can allow the prediction of endurance limit associated with damage onset in composites containing artificial flaws and exposed under different environmental conditions[3]. The methodology is based on the generation of the S/N curves related to fatigue damage initiation by using complementary health monitoring techniques such acoustic emission technique (AE), ultrasonic guided waves and damage image correlation techniques (DIC) [2]. Experimental mechanical tests based on mode I, mode II and mixed mode (I,II) and fracture mechanic calculations [4], based on strain energy release rates were used to develop failure criteria for delamination initiation in the objective to establish a fatigue life prediction model for used composites [5]. This paper presents an original approach based principally on acoustic emission monitoring to determine fatigue life thresholds to damage initiation obtained in composites with embedded artificial flaws. The principal objective is to assess the influence of inserted artificial defects on the fatigue behavior of plain weave composites and to evaluate experimentally, the effect of environmental factors such as humidity and temperature on the fatigue life thresholds for damage onset.

The first part of this study combines two health monitoring techniques to determine fatigue life curves and to estimate stiffness degradation for plain weave composites containing flaws. Damage monitoring by acoustic emission will provide S/N curves associated with damage onset appearing in the coupons and S/N curves related to the propagation of embedded artificial flaw. Acoustic emission (AE) is among a few methods that possess the potential for continuously detecting the occurrence and growth of damage and possibly quantifying damage in a structure under service conditions. Acoustic emission (AE) phenomenon are related to the movement and growth of damage in materials which generates elastic stress waves by releasing elastic energy stored in the composite material. Instead, to detect discontinuities in the material such as ultrasonic inspection does, AE detects micro failures associated with the fiber, matrix cracking, interface damage, and macroscopic delamination. The amount of detected AE signal energy is strongly correlated to elastic energy released within composites by damage evolution processes. A significant benefit of AE monitoring is that it allows the whole testing material to be assessed non-intrusively during in-service loading, besides detecting damage earlier than any other technique. Digital image correlation (DIC) technique was the second monitoring technique applied in this work. This method relies on the comparison between a reference

photograph of the loaded specimen captured by two individual cameras and the same picture taken while the sample withstands deformations. The correlation algorithm compares the two stored digital images, thanks to the random speckle pattern applied previously on the coupon and permits access to in and out of plane displacements and in-plane strains of the surface by calculating the displacement field through cross-correlation function.

In summary, the first part of the paper investigates the use of hybrid monitoring approach to generate fatigue life (S/N) curves related to damage onset and also to quantify the degradation of mechanical properties as a function of fatigue life and damage accumulation. Damage monitoring by using acoustic emission technique will provide fatigue life curves corresponding to the macroscopic delamination growth generated by artificial flaws. Finally, the DIC monitoring technique will help to assess the stiffness reduction due to the propagation of delamination under fatigue cycling. This investigation will focus on evaluating the stiffness degradation in the region which contains the artificial embedded flaw, in opposition besides the global stiffness degradation of the material.

The second part of the article will focus on the measurement of delamination resistance to modes I, II and mixed loading and to develop analytical model to predict fatigue life curves. Appropriate ASTM standard tests based on the mode I (double cantilever beam), mode II (end-notched flexure), and mixed-mode fracture toughness were investigated. For the mixed mode loading, experimental testing examines three distinct rates of strain release rate G_{II} / G_{max} . Composites coupons were submitted to static and fatigue loading for ambient and different environmental conditions. The interlaminar fracture toughness results and extracted AE data were used to establish delamination initiation failure criteria. This series of tests aims at detecting delamination initiation and constructing a fatigue curve in term of strain energy release rates as a function of the number of cycles such as $\Delta G = f(N)$. The results will be merged with a finite element modeling and a Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) calculation to generate the fatigue life prediction model. The development of such a model will be presented in further publication.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

a) S/N curves generation

The examined composite material to generate S/N curves was a plain-weave (0/90) carbon fiber reinforced epoxy laminate made as an eight plies laminate of stacking sequence $[40, 0, -45, 90]_s$, with dimensions of $304.8 \times 76.2 \times 1.62 \text{ mm}^3$. Test coupons with an artificial flaw created by embedding a Teflon tape in the lay-up between (-45, 90) layers with dimensions $12.7 \times 12.7 \text{ mm}^2$, centered on the coupons, were used. The specimens were repeatedly subjected to the range of axial stress history under tension-tension fatigue loading under constant amplitude cycling until total failure. Fatigue load levels were chosen by performing quasi-static tests monitored by acoustic emission at room temperature. All mechanical tests were carried out on an MTS 100 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine under load-controlled mode. The load was transferred to the specimens through hydraulic grips, which sustained a constant pressure of 16 MPa at each extremity. Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted under constant amplitude sinusoidal function with cycling frequency of 7 Hz and 15 Hz and stress ratio R of 0.1. The assessment of the effect of the combination of high-temperature exposure and moisture is achieved by testing 18 samples under 82 °C with 85% of humidity, nine samples under 7Hz and nine samples under 15Hz loading frequency, and also nine samples were tested under 25 °C with 85% of humidity. Table 1 displays the number of specimens used in this experimental testing part, and the types of environmental conditioning applied to the samples during the static and fatigue loading to generate S/N curves.

The environmental conditions are simulated in a heat chamber by controlling the temperature and the entry of humidity provided by a Thermotron SE-type 300 conditioner installed next to the MTS machine. An extensometer system camera was used to measure the longitudinal strain on the sample through the window of the thermal chamber during the fatigue testing.

	Static testing		Fatigue testing, R=0.1						
Condition	RT*		RT		25°C & 85%	82°C & 85%		82°C & Dry	120°C & Dry
Cyclic frequency	N.A		7Hz	15Hz	15Hz	7Hz	15Hz	15Hz	7Hz
Number of tested samples	6	6	5	6	9	9	9	9	10

Table 1: Fatigue sample number and conditions of temperature and humidity exposure

This system has been synchronized with the controller of the MTS machine to provide automatic control during fatigue testing. Two thermocouples installed on the surface of the sample were used to monitor the temperature of the sample during the tests. A hygrometer has also been placed in the testing chamber to monitor the level of moisture (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Fatigue testing and surveillance under controlled moisture and temperature using Thermotron conditioner.

b) Failure criteria development by calculating strain energy release rates

Fracture mechanics test methods measure the interlaminar fracture toughness as a critical value of strain energy release rate G_C associated with a sufficient accumulation of strain energy in the structure to cause delamination onset and growth. The main failure modes are by way of mode I (tensile opening), sliding or shear (mode II and III) and a mixture of opening and sliding (mixed-mode). Each of these modes is associated to an experimental procedure: dual cantilever beam (DCB) for mode I, end notch flexure (ENF) for mode II and mixed-mode bending (MMB) for mixed-mode. Schematic representations of the different sample loading are shown in Figure 2. The black arrow represents the applied load P , $2h$ the thickness, $2L$ the length, a crack length, and c the length of the lever, which controls the mixed-mode. Then, the second series of samples was tested to construct an onset delamination fatigue curve $\Delta G = f(N)$. The tested samples were prepared with G30-500 PW taffeta fabric carbon fiber pre-impregnated with CYCOM 5276-1 Epoxy. The stacking sequence used is $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$, with a $10 \mu\text{m}$ Teflon insert at mid-plane to create initial delamination. The samples have a rectangular shape (150 x 25 mm) with a 3 mm thickness. The initial delamination a_0 is 25 mm long. Also, a set of samples have been conditioned in a temperature and humidity controlled environment at 82°C and 85 % of moisture during 30 days, then sealed and tested in a temperature controlled chamber.

Figure 2: Experimental approaches to delamination mode measurements

All tests at ambient temperature were conducted on an MTS Test Frame 322 with a 5 kN load cell, and tests at high temperature were conducted on an MTS Landmark 370 with a 2.5 kN load cell, coupled with an MTS environmental chamber. Hinges were glued with an epoxy-based adhesive and drilled accordingly to the standard MMB apparatus from ASTM. The support span $2L$ was fixed to 120 mm. A layer of nail polish was applied on the edges of the samples, and then each millimeter of propagation was marked. Through a Dinolite camera x70, it was possible to follow the spread of the delamination. The control displacement was set at 0.5 mm/mn.

Figure 3: MMB delamination testing

To construct an onset delamination fatigue curve $\Delta G = f(N)$. All tests were conducted at 7 Hz under displacement control with a load ratio of $G_{min}/G_{max} = 0.1$. Each sample was loaded in static previously at the fatigue experiment to determine the maximum and minimum displacement δ_{max} and δ_{min} , corresponding respectively to G_{max} and G_{min} . The test was stopped at a 10 cycles interval on the maximum plateaus to measure the delamination length. This interval increases with the number of cycles. The delamination onset was monitored from a 5% drop of the load and by collecting AE signals. The AE data acquisition system used during the experiments is provided by Mistras group. The measurement system shown in figure 1 includes four piezoelectric sensors from PAC. The used WD piezoelectric sensors have a broad frequency response band up to 1 MHz, which had a maximum sensitivity between 125 kHz and 450 kHz. Each sensor is connected to a preamplifier that transmits analogic signals to an eight-channel acquisition and treatment unit μ DISP. The AE signals data are therefore gathered and stored digitally on a computer via a PCI connection bus using *AEWin* software.

The signal processing, feature extraction, data management, and manipulation were performed by *AEWin* Post software. After each test, the AE signals were further analyzed using Noesis Software from Mistras. The AE monitoring configuration for damage localization uses four WD sensors. In the case of the mechanical tests aimed to monitor the propagation of delamination under mixed mode loading, two sensors were used and placed at the bottom of the samples, one next to the initial crack and the other at the sample's end. In the case of high-temperature testing, only one sensor was placed, as shown in Figure 3 and fixed with a clipping system.

3 RESULTS

a) S/N curves generation results and estimation of stiffness degradation

Preliminary quasi-static tension tests were applied to both unflawed (NFS) and coupons with embedded flaws (WFS) to determine the static strength of composites samples, and also to distinguish the applied stress levels from which the composite generate acoustic emission waves. These stress values define the “acoustic emission threshold,” indicating the onset of matrix and interface micro-failures in the laminate. The obtained threshold values were used to set the limit states of the load levels to be applied during fatigue testing. Several samples were tested at different load levels to generate fatigue life curves associated with both, initiation of damage and complete failure of the composite coupons. The detection of damage initiation around embedded flaws was obtained by the application of the planar AE source localization method, to locate the emergent micro damages and delaminations in the region around the artificial defect, and to determine fatigue life threshold associated to damage initiation and artificial flaw propagation. For ambient temperature fatigue testing, two cycling frequencies were considered 7Hz and 15Hz. The identified cycle numbers that correspond to damage initiation thresholds, identified by AE detection, were used to generate the S-N fatigue curves, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: S/N curve of flaw propagation and failure obtained by AE monitoring for 7 and 15 Hz.

The predictive models are represented by the following analytical expression $(\sigma/\sigma_{UTS})=a+b.\log(N)$, where a and b are the intercept and the slope of the curve. The solid lines represent the S-N curves corresponding to the complete failure of the composite samples. The dashed line curves correspond to the S-N curves outlining the propagation of the artificial flaw detected by AE localization methods. Figure 3 shows that the effect of the cycling frequency on flaw propagation is more pronounced for 53% UTL loading case than for the high load's levels such as 59% and 65% UTL. Figure 4 shows the effect of combined action of humidity and temperature on the fatigue life curves. The S/N curves were compared with those obtained during the fatigue test on samples tested at a frequency of 7Hz under ambient temperature condition (RT). This comparison makes it possible to evaluate the influence of

the combined effect of temperature and humidity on the generation of damage around the inserted flaw. These curves show that damage initiation thresholds for the samples tested under RT condition appear at higher cycle numbers than in the case of samples, which have undergone the combined effect of temperature and moisture.

Figure 5: S/N curve of flaw propagation and failure obtained by AE under RT and 82°C-85%.

The stiffness degradation caused by fatigue loading was determined using the DIC system based on the average strain field measured over the area of interest. Figure 6 shows the normalized stiffness modulus (E/E_0) for the NFS and WFS configurations, respectively. E_0 is the initial specimen stiffness measured at the beginning of the test, and E is the updated stiffness determined after N cycles. Different stiffness degradation patterns were found for the two configurations. Considering the NFS, the stiffness evolution exhibits a typical profile with three degradation phases, as shown in the literature. A rapid decrease of approximately 9% occurred within the first 20% of the fatigue life. This degradation is caused by micro-structural damage such as matrix micro-cracking, fiber/matrix interfacial debonding, and transverse cracks in the fill. This step is followed by a continuous slow decrease, which encompasses the major part of the fatigue life. The damage mechanisms attributed to this phase are a shear failure in the warp and the onset and propagation of delamination between the fill and warp as well as between adjacent layers. The transition between phase II and phase III occurs at the last 5-10% of the fatigue life, in which the stiffness drops rapidly promoted by damage multiplication, particularly due to strands fractures on the 0° plies, leading to the final failure. The total average stiffness decay measured prior failure for the three NFS was approximately 20%.

However, in WFS, the stiffness decays more rapidly following a quasi-linear degradation but remain higher than that registered for the NFS at the final failure. The total stiffness decay for the three specimens varies between [10 to 18%], which is following the lower amount of damage observed previously in the failed coupons. As mentioned earlier, the important reduction in fatigue life caused by the artificial delamination could be attributed to the strain and shear stress concentration introduced by the flaw. Indeed, beginning in the first cycles, the strain field around the defect exhibits higher values than within the rest of the plate. This high strain region increased over fatigue life and spread to cover a larger area. Fig 7 illustrates the evolution of the longitudinal strain fields during three different fatigue stages obtained by DIC. The last stage of this map (Fig 7) emphasizes the spread and the linking between free-edge damage and interlaminar delamination initiated from the artificial flaw which leads to the final failure of the structure as localized AE sources activities demonstrated it.

Figure 6: Normalized stiffness degradation of NFS and WFS over the fatigue life

Figure 7: Evolution of the longitudinal strain field over the normalized fatigue life

b) Failure criteria development by calculating strain energy release rates

This part presents an experimental methodology based on Acoustic Emission (AE) detection to estimate the onset of delamination in plain weave carbon fiber coupons, under quasi-static and fatigue loading, at different mixed-mode ratios ($G_{II}/G_T = 0, 0.28, 0.46, 0.75$ and 1) and under various environmental conditions (ambient temperature and dry, 82°C and dry, 82°C and 85% humidity). Under fatigue loading, different energy release rate ratios G_{max}/G_c were tested, to generate a 3D initiation criteria in fatigue as $G_{max} = f(G_{II}/G_T, N)$. These experimental results will be used further in a fatigue life prediction model for a plain weave composite structure containing an embedded flaw. For fatigue, the load ratio $G_{min}/G_{max} = 0.1$ was chosen to avoid AE noise generation from friction and slipping. The acquisition threshold remained the same as in quasi-static but will be modified in post-processing treatment to determine its impact on the number of received signals. Figure 3 shows a typical evolution of the AE signal's amplitude collected during an MMB test. A first significant peak in the amplitude can be observed around 400 seconds of mechanical test that can be associated with the delamination onset. A similar analysis was conducted with the evolution of the energy and number of counts, parameters that are directly related to delamination onset in quasi-static, and compared to the trend of the amplitude evolution.

Figure 8: Evolution of the AE signals' amplitude through time during an MMB test

Figure 8 compares the total strain energy release rate obtained from the ASTM and AE delamination onset methodology at the three environmental conditions tested. The ASTM delamination onset corresponds to the maximum load observed before the crack propagation. Under mixed-mode loading, the critical value G_c corresponds to the sum of the G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} components. The failure envelopes were obtained from a polynomial law used to fit the experimental data. The AE delamination onset envelope is a more severe failure criterion, as it appeared at lower energy than the maximum load methodology from ASTM. However, it represents in a better way the accumulation of damage before the crack expands.

Figure 9. Failure envelop of the tested materials from ASTM and AE results, at 20°C, 82°C and 82°C + 85%RH

To analyze delamination onset under fatigue loading, each sample was loaded at a G_{max} value corresponding to a wanted percentage of the quasi-static critical energy G_c . For each pure modes and mixed-mode ratios, the G_{max} values oscillated between 30% and 70% of G_c . Tests were conducted until a significant crack is observed on the edge of the samples or until $2 \cdot 10^4$ cycles. This ultimate limit was reached only on two samples for a very low value of G_{max} under mode II loading. The delamination onset curves obtained from fatigue testing at 20°C are presented in Figure 9. Full lines are obtained from a linear fitting of the data in a semi-log representation, given by the following equation: $G_{max} = a + b \cdot \log(N)$.

Figure 10: Delamination onset curves from AE onset criterion under pure modes and mixed-mode loading at 20°C

To assess the delamination onset, for any mixed-mode ratio, a delamination onset surface needs to be calculated from the two dimensions G-N curves. As an example, the 3D surface failure obtained from AE delamination onset methodology is presented in Figure 11. The equation of this surface is directly extracted from the quasi-static failure envelopes and the evolution of the slopes of the G-N curves fitting when the mixed-mode ratio changes. This equation will be used further in the fatigue life predictive model.

Figure 11: Delamination onset surface under fatigue loading at 20°C

Other 3D surfaces were generated for each environmental conditions, 20°C, 82°C and 82°C + 85%H. The same methodology was used, with 40 experimental data points for each case. The obtained results were in the same trend, with lower values of G_{max}, giving an approximate 8% drop at 82 °C and a 10% drop at 82°C + 85%H. From each obtained 3D surface envelope, a failure criterion is defined according to the form of an analytical equation as follow:

$$\frac{G_{\max}}{G_{IIc}} = X - Y \cdot \log(N)$$

$$X = a_1 + b_1 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + c_1 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$

$$Y = a_2 + b_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right) + c_2 \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_T} \right)^2$$
(1)

where $a_1, b_1, c_1, a_2, b_2, c_2$, are the coefficients of the equations that will be determined by the 3D surface fitting. The obtained equations are used to predict the fatigue curves for the ambient temperature and for the environmental conditions under consideration. The results will be published elsewhere.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The development of a monitoring strategy based on the location of AE sources has allowed generating fatigue life curves successfully. These curves were used to determine the fatigue life corresponding to the spread of delamination from an artificial defect inserted into the material. The generation and comparison of S-N curves under different test conditions helped to highlight the influence upon the cyclic frequency, temperature, and the combined effect of temperature and moisture on fatigue life. The following conclusions were reached; first, it has been observed that the increase in temperature greatly reduces the fatigue life of the samples. This effect is caused by the degradation of the matrix at high temperature. Second, the presence of moisture plays a significant role in fatigue life. The moisture absorbed by the samples degrades the mechanical properties of the polymer matrix composite. This deterioration is more critical when combining the humidity and the temperature, which favoring the early cracking of the composite and facilitating the propagation of the artificial defect, consequently, the reduction of the fatigue lifetime of the composite. In the second part of this investigation, acoustic emission monitoring was used to determine fatigue delamination onset during cyclic loading based on fracture mechanics approach. A methodology was developed and used to produce 3D delamination onset envelope for mode I, mode II and mixed mode I and II fatigue loading. The 3D surface obtained from this experimental work will be used further in a fatigue life prediction model of composite with an embedded flaw, associated with a finite element model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge the Consortium of Research and Innovation in Aerospace in Quebec (CRIAQ), Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), Bombardier Aerospace, L-3 MAS and MITACS for their funding.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tay, TE. (2003). Characterization and analysis of delamination fracture in composites: An overview of developments from 1990 to 2001. *Applied Mechanics Reviewers*, 56(1).
- [2] Silversides, I., Maslouhi, A., and Laplante, G. 2013, "Acoustic Emission Monitoring of Interlaminar Delamination Onset in Carbon Fibre Composites", *Structural Health Monitoring*, 12(2), pp. 126-140.
- [3] Krueger, R., Paris, I.L., O'Brien, T.K., and Minguet, PJ. 2001, "Fatigue life methodology for bonded composite skin/stringer configurations", *NASA/TM*, 210842.
- [4] ASTM D 6671/D 6671M – 03. Standard Test Method for Mixed mode I-Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites.
- [5] Reeder, J. and Crews J. (1990). Mixed-Mode Bending method for Delamination Testing. *AIAA Journal*, 28(7), 1270-1276.